

STUDIES IN THE *cyclo*HEXANE SERIES. PART I. THE SYNTHESIS OF *cyclo*HEXANE-1:1-DICARBOXYLIC ACID

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*cyclo*Hexane-1:1-dicarboxylic acid has been synthesised by a new method. 1-Carboxy*cyclo*hexane-1-acetic acid was brominated to the bromo-acid (I), which on treatment with sodium carbonate afforded the corresponding hydroxy-acid (II). Alkaline oxidation of this acid yielded *cyclo*hexane-1:1-dicarboxylic acid.

There exist in literature a number of methods for the synthesis of *cyclo*alkane-1:1-dicarboxylic acids. Thus, *cyclo*hexane-1:1-dicarboxylic acid (m.p. 179.5°) was prepared by Dox and Yoder (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 43, 1366) by condensing the di-iodo derivative of ethyl malonate with 1:5-dibromopentane, and hydrolysing the resulting ester with ethanolic potassium hydroxide. The same acid was prepared by Ingold and Thorpe (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 376), melting at 207°, but it was later corrected by Weighman (*ibid.*, 1926, 2543). Vogel (*ibid.*, 1929, 1488) and Kharasch *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 2976) reported the acid to melt at 176° (decomp.).

In the present method followed by us *cyclo*hexanone was condensed with ethyl cyanoacetate, following the directions suggested by Cope *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 3452). Ethyl *cyclo*hexylidene cyanoacetate was then treated with ethanolic potassium cyanide to afford ethyl 1-cyanocyclohexane-1- α -cyanoacetate, which on hydrolysis with concentrated hydrochloric acid furnished 1-carboxy*cyclo*hexane-1-acetic acid. This acid was earlier prepared by Norris and Thorpe (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 1199), Ingold *et al.* (*ibid.*, 1923, 123, 853) and Dickens, Horton and Thorpe (*ibid.*, 1924, 125, 1830). Bromination of this acid furnished 1-carboxy*cyclo*hexane-1- α -bromoacetic acid (I), which on subsequent hydrolysis with sodium carbonate solution (2*N*) yielded 1-carboxy*cyclo*hexane-1- α -hydroxyacetic acid (II). This glycollic acid was then oxidised with alkaline potassium permanganate when *cyclo*hexane-1:1-dicarboxylic acid (III), m.p. 176° (decomp.), was obtained.

This method was developed by Desai, Hunter and Salaria (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1942, 15A, 150) for the preparation of 4- and 3-methyl*cyclo*hexane-1:1-dicarboxylic acids. It is useful because of its simplicity and general applicability. However, the authenticity of this method was recently questioned by Price *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 2301) who repeated the work of Desai *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) and were unable to isolate any 4-methyl*cyclo*hexane-1:1-dicarboxylic acid. In order to establish the authenticity of this method, we have successfully carried out the preparation of *cyclo*hexane-1:1-dicarboxylic acid, m.p. 176° (decomp.), which remains undepressed on taking the mixed melt with an authentic sample of the acid, synthesised by the method of Dox and Yoder (*loc. cit.*). Thus, it is found that the alkaline permanganate oxidation of

the glycollic acid (II) does give rise to cyclohexane-1:1-dicarboxylic acid, though in small yields.

This work has since then been also extended to the preparation of the cycloheptane analogue (Saharia, *Proc. Ind. Sci. Congress*, 1957, Part III, p. 137) and the complete results which are in full agreement with our earlier observations will soon be published in detail.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl cyclohexylidenecyanoacetate.—cyclohexanone (58.8 g., 0.6M), ethyl cyanoacetate (56.5 g., 0.5 M), glacial acetic acid (6 g., 0.1 M), ammonium acetate (3.9 g., 0.36 M) and benzene (60 c.c.) were taken in a round bottom flask (250 c.c.) attached to a modified Dean and Stark constant water separator and then to a reflux condenser. The contents were heated in an oil-bath at 120-60° till there was no more separation of water (4-6 hours). The resulting product was cooled and the benzene solution washed with water (100 c.c. × 3). The washings were extracted twice with two small portions of benzene and the benzene solutions combined. After removing benzene, the residue was distilled under reduced pressure when the first running consisted of cyclohexanone and ethyl cyanoacetate and the main bulk of ethyl cyclohexylidenecyanoacetate distilled at 150-52°/9-10 mm (yield 78 g., 81%). Cope *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 2327; 1941, 63, 3452) record b.p. 150°/9 mm and 146-47°/9 mm.

Ethyl 1-Cyanocyclohexane-1-α-cyanoacetate.—Ethyl cyclohexylidenecyanoacetate (78 g., 0.4 M) was dissolved in ethanol (390 c.c., 95%) and to it was added potassium cyanide (54.5 g., 0.84M), dissolved in water (120 c.c.), in small lots, with constant shaking and cooling under the water tap. After keeping the contents at room temperature for 48 hours, alcohol was removed at the pump and the residue acidified with HCl. The separated thick oily layer was extracted with ether, the ethereal solution dried and the ether stripped off. The residue was distilled at 168-69°/7-8 mm to furnish pure ethyl 1-cyanocyclohexane-1-α-cyanoacetate which solidified to a hard mass and on crystallisation from ethanol melted at 54° (Dickens *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, report the b.p. 210-12°/22 mm and m.p. 54°).

During the working up of the above dicyano ester, 1-cyanocyclohexane-1-acetonitrile (IV), m.p. 83-84°, was also obtained (Dickens *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, report its m.p. 84.5°).

1-Carboxycyclohexane-1-acetic Acid.—Ethyl 1-cyanocyclohexane-1-α-cyanoacetate (55 g.) was refluxed with HCl (conc., 400 c.c.) on a sand-bath for 16 hours. After cooling, the contents were extracted thrice with ether and the ethereal layer was washed with

sodium carbonate solution (10%). The alkaline extract on acidification with HCl (conc.) deposited the acid, m.p. 130-31°. On treatment with animal charcoal and two crystallisations from water the pure acid melting at 132° (lit. m.p. 133°) was obtained in 75% yield. The same acid was also obtained by the hydrolysis of the above dinitrile (IV).

1-Carboxycyclohexane-1- α -bromoacetic Acid.—PCl₅ (32.5 g.) was slowly added to finely powdered 1-carboxycyclohexane-1-acetic acid (14.5 g.) contained in a small r.b. flask, and cooled. When the initial reaction had subsided, the contents were refluxed on a water-bath (6 hours). On cooling, bromine (12 g., 4.5 c.c.) was added in small lots with occasional shaking (6 hours); a crystal of iodine was then added and after exposing to sunlight (6-8 hours) the contents were heated in an oil-bath at 50-60° for 36 hours. The bromo-acid chloride, thus formed, was decomposed first in the cold and then on the water-bath (3-4 hours) with formic acid (98-100%) with constant stirring. On cooling, the bromo-acid separated out, m.p. 115-21°, yield 17.5 g., 85%.

On refluxing with petroleum ether (b.p. 50°) the insoluble portion on recrystallisation from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether mixture had m.p. 142.5°. [Found: C, 40.6; H, 4.7; equiv., 134.2. C₈H₁₃O₄Br requires C, 40.7; H, 4.9%; equiv., 132.5 (dibasic)].

1-Carboxycyclohexane-1-glycollic Acid.—The preceding bromoacetic acid (14 g.) was neutralised with sodium carbonate solution (2N) and refluxed on a sand-bath (4 hours). On cooling and acidification with HCl (conc.) and after saturation with ammonium sulphate, the product was continuously extracted with ether (8 hours); the ethereal solution was dried and the solvent removed. The residue was kept in vacuum and on trituration with dry benzene a colorless solid was obtained melting at 131-32°. Recrystallisation from benzene furnished the pure *glycollic acid*, m.p. 132°, yield 8.5 g., 80%. [Found: C, 53.5; H, 5.8; equiv., 100.8. C₈H₁₄O₅ requires C, 53.4; H, 6.9%; equiv., 101 (dibasic)].

cycloHexane-1:1-dicarboxylic Acid.—The preceding acid (4 g.) was neutralised with N/20-Ba(OH)₂ solution and to this was slowly added KMnO₄ (8 g.), dissolved in 1 litre of water, with constant stirring during 4 hours. After keeping at room temperature for 16-18 hours, SO₂ was passed to eliminate the excess of permanganate, and filtered. To the clear solution NaOH was added and the alkaline solution concentrated to a small bulk, acidified with HCl (conc.) in the cold and saturated with ammonium sulphate. This was then continuously extracted with ether (8 hours) and the ethereal solution dried. The solvent was then removed and the residue kept in vacuum, which on trituration with dry benzene furnished a solid melting at 171-72° (efferv.). On recrystallisation from ethyl acetate it melted at 176° (efferv.). Mixed m.p. with the authentic specimen prepared by the method of Dox and Yoder (*loc. cit.*) remained undepressed (yield 0.15 g.). (Found: C, 55.7; H, 6.8. Calc. for C₈H₁₂O₄: C, 55.8; H, 7.0%). Its diamide, prepared in the customary manner, had m.p. 260° (lit m.p. 261°).

The analyses were carried out in the Microanalytical laboratory of this Department.